

Muthiri Kinaru at Swamithoppu Pathi

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Abstract

Munthiri Kinaru (well) assumes a significant part in joining individuals in this piece of the nation, breaking the caste-based segregation that once won among them. Previously and during the time of Lord Vaikundar, this piece of the subcontinent was under the grasp of feudalism, casteism, and distance. There were independent wells and tanks for every station, and individuals from the other standing were not permitted to draw water from those wells. As in the Vinchai, since the social point of 'uplifting the lowly treated individuals in the public possesses a significant part in the profound mission of Vaikundar, which is projected towards the ideal Dharma Yukam, he needed to stop this malicious practise. As an initial step sanathana dharma was laid out at Swamithoppe. Besides strict holiness, this very much was additionally a recorded symbol since it was the main well in this piece of the nation where individuals could use water openly, regardless of their position.

Keywords: Muthiri Kinaru, Lord Vaikundar, Swamithoppe, Ayyavazhi, Patham

Introduction

Muthiri Kinaru is a holy very much situated in the north-western corner of Swamithoppe town. This is the popular theertha of the sanctuary. It is found a large portion a kilometre west of the fundamental Pathi. After finishing the Six-year Tavam of Vaikundar in 1840, the Thuvayal Thavasus rehearsed at Vakaipathi and Muttappathi for around one year as they arrived at Swamithoppe. A few ceremonial acts of Ayyavazhi began from this. Some, particularly the requests have gone on as followed during the Thuvayal Thavasus period, and some began according to the guidelines of Vaikundar. In that series, Akilathirattu talks about that well as "the eighteen standings collecting in one spot, and washing from a similar well". This alludes to the pervasiveness of an apparently harmless act of individuals, assembled around Vaikundar, washing together from the water of this well. Individuals of various standings washed together at this well, thoughtless of their social distinctions. Actual closeness was required, chiefly because of the littleness of the well. Other than washing, they drank this water as a solution for their sickness. They prepare their food with the utilisation of this water and eat in the local area feast alongside Vaikundar. On occasions, the well and its water appear to have procured strict importance to individuals of Ayyavazhi. The demonstration of washing, drinking, and preparing the food with this water came to be rehashed with custom enthusiasm. Individuals started to think about the well as a consecrated one, and the water as having an inexplicable ability to recuperate ailment. A couplet from the Saattu Neettolai of Arul Nool peruse as "everybody is drinking the milk of the well around

which marvels are developing". After this statement, it appears to be that Akilam itself certifies the well as a sacrosanct one. Individuals think of it as a strict commitment to wash and drink essentially a couple of drops of water from this well. Many individuals and different standings congregated there to draw water for washing and drinking. Ayya Vaikuntar utilized the blessed water from the well and the heavenly mud to fix individuals of their ailments.

The Formation of Well

The Inner View of Patham Drawn from Muthirikkinaru (Well)

In the then Travancore society, the unfair laws of immaculateness and contamination were exceptionally touchy in spots of washing and such acts, including the utilization of water. Division of independent spots for the various standings for washing and drawing water, and severe implementation of this segregated partition through guidelines, social and political, alongside solid strict assent, ss was the thing to get done. As an overall custom, the lower standings were restricted from drawing water from public wells and lakes. The upper caste individuals had separate wells so they could keep away from the presence and contamination of the lower standing individuals. The individuals who, be it an individual from the standing fold or one from outside it, dared to violate these divided spaces were punished with extreme beatings or even wiped out unceremoniously. Against this foundation, a custom including the assemblage of individuals from various ranks around a well, washing together, and preparing their food with the water of a similar very much was being performed at Swamithoppe, where Ayya Vaikundar was completing his main goal. It was an aberrant test of the malevolent arrangement of unapproachability. This bunch of ceremonial activities put into high gear a cross-examination of the arrangement of virtue and contamination and tested the authoritative arrangement of segregated detachment in a roundabout way. The ceremonial limits set on the utilization of water were looked to be violated, and the strength of the conventional teaching on custom debasement suggested in the trading of water starting with one then onto the next, was attempted to be debilitated.

Wonders of the Divine Well

The customary Pattai, which is made of Palmyra leaf, used to draw water from the holy Muthirikkinaru. Because of the consideration zeroed in on the well, noxious demonstrations have been recorded where the toxin was two times put into the water by some enemy of ayyavazhi components. One was during Vaikundar and was noted in Akilam and

one more was at a new time. It has been accounted for that Lord Vaikundar gathered the toxin into a Sivalinga and the Sivalinga stayed inside the well in the main harming. According to Akilathirattu, individuals, catching wind of the harming announced it to Vaikundar and mentioned to him to save them. Vaikundar informed the enthusiasts that the water in the all around was non-harmful. Individuals who had confidence as would be natural for him drank and washed in the well and were absolutely protected. The people who had no faith in a way that would sound natural to him and had plastered the water became oblivious. Individuals raced to the Lord and portrayed the occurrence. The ruler requested that they sprinkle the heavenly water on the individuals who were oblivious. They got up as though from sleep. Then on 17 September 1994, the principal Sunday of the Tamil Month, Puratasi, poison was stirred up in the sacrosanct water of Muthirikkinaru for the subsequent time. A few lowlife inundated a 5-kilogram parcel of poison, a profoundly harmful synthetic, into the well. There was a smell of this substance wherever around the well. A few exhorted the enthusiasts not to wash in the well. Yet, no one noticed it; a great many individuals washed in and drank the water. Indeed, even half year old infants were washed here, yet no one was impacted. The unfilled bundle of the synthetic was subsequently recovered and annihilated. This well is treated with more significance since it is joined to the incarnational exercises of Vaikundar. To conquer the three varieties Anava, Kanma, and Maya, one ought to accomplish profound neatness, and this tidiness is acquired when one washes from this consecrated well. This well is supposed to be fixed by Vaikundar and will stay as a symbol for destructing Kali. Indeed, even today, the well is too packed to even consider washing. Individuals drink this water as Patham. The heavenly water from this well will deal with one for the existence of Dharma Yukam. It is likewise trusted that maniacs and patients, having no fix even after delayed clinical treatment and a stay in the sanctuary, can wash up in muthirikinaru and be cured. The water level in this well will continue as before regardless of how dry it is. Regardless of how much water you take, the water level doesn't drop. It is the brilliance of Ayya Vaikunda Swami that the water of this well is cool in summer and youthful in winter. The water in this well is said to have been fixed by the lovers of Ayyavazhi.

Regular Rituals

The Muthirikkinaru tends to in Akilam as Muthal Thalam. The Payyans began their day-to-day timetable solely after the strict washing in this well. After the stately shower, they used to drink the sacrosanct water (Patham) of the Muthirikkinaru for multiple times and give it so to the adherents multiple times. Then, the Payyan circumambulates the Muthirikkinaru multiple times and others follow him. Reciting "Ayya Siva Siva-siva Ara-hara Ara-hara," are the slogan procedures in the Pathi. This is drilled threefold per day in the first part of the day, early afternoon, and evening in Panividais. Likewise, one of the significant ceremonial activities performed by the fans of Ayyavazhi is to have this custom shower, drawing water from a well. This has turned into a custom need to go through, before entering to adore at the

Path. It is overpowering to see the fans crowd the well to get a couple of containers of water on to them and drink a couple of drops ceremoniously multiple times and then continue to the Path. This act of washing at the well is being tended to as Patham viduthal.

On Festival Time

Besides this everyday custom, this Muthirikkinaru procures strict importance during the eighth day of the Kodiyettru Dhammakaya celebration. On that day, Lord Vaikundar is conveyed to muthirikinaru on a pony (vahana). The God chases Kali. The stylised hunting of kali is finished with a bow and bolt. Here, a great many individuals gathered to drink the blessed parham. Patham viduthal is the word used by the enthusiasts for washing in Muthirikinaru. There is a weighty hurry to have a shower in the well on the primary Sunday of the Tamil months. Arul Nool, the optional blessed book, encourages doing Dharma close to this admirably. During the Car celebrations and during the Vaikunda Jayanthi festivities, the admirers are not permitted to draw water from Muthirikkinaru because of the restricted size of the well and the degree of the group that goes to adore. During those days, a couple of Panividaiyalar were used to draw water from the well and to toss it onto the group. Thusly, everybody in the group gets a couple of drops poured on their heads.

Conclusion

The aim of Sri Vaikunda Swami was to elevate the modest treated individuals in the public arena to involve a significant part in the otherworldly mission of Vaikundar, which is projected towards the best Dharma Yukam; he needed to stop this underhanded practice. So as the initial step to arrive at this point, this very much was laid out at Swamithoppe. Besides strict holiness, this very much was additionally an authentic symbol since it was the primary well in this piece of the nation where individuals could use water uninhibitedly, independent of their station. Many individuals and different positions congregated there to draw water for washing and drinking. Ayya Vaikuntar utilized the heavenly water from a well and the sacred mud to fix individuals with their ailments.

References

- [1] Patrick, G. *Religion and Subaltern Agency*, University of Madras, 2003.
- [2] Ponnu, R. *Sri Vaikunda Swamigal and Struggle for Social Equality in South India*, Ram Publishers, 2000.
- [3] Krishnanathan, T. *Ayya Vaikundarin Vazhvum Sinthanaiyum*, Madurai Kamaraj University, Thina Publications, Nagercoil, 2000.
- [4] Vivekanandan, N. *Akilathirattu Ammanai Moolamum Uraiyum* (Part 1&2), Vivekananda Publications, Nagercoil, 2003.
- [5] Arisundara Mani, A. *Akilathirattu Ammanai Parayana Urai*, Ayya Vaikundar Thirukkudumbam Publications, Nagercoil, 2002.
- [6] Manibharathi, A. *Akilathirattu Vilakka Urai*, Thirunamappukazh Publications, Chennai, 2003.

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[7] Amalan. *Ayya Vaikundar Punitha Varalaru*, Akilam Publications, 2000.

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